

Absolute shifting times are not statistically grounded for reporting circadian burden

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We contest Weed and Zeitzer [1]’s claim that total absolute shifting times are “physiologically grounded” and show that it is the standard deviation SD that provides a statistically, physiologically grounded metric of shifting times yearly variability. We show that the magnitude of the predictor in Weed and Zeitzer [2] is extremely weak and that, by design, authors’ methodology inevitably yields worst scores for the current seasonal clock policy.

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Weed and Zeitzer maintain in their appreciated reply[1] to the Letter by Erren et al.[3] and our Letter[4] that the use of yearly accumulated absolute shifting times to assess the circadian burden in a model is “physiologically grounded”. Respectfully, it may not be.

Figure 1 (top) shows the authors’ original phase, with a stabilized value, aside from clock transition dates, and weak fluctuations (noise), similar to the time step of the model ($\delta = 5$ min or 0.3% of a day). This variability results in small shifting times (close-neighbor differences) with zero average and with standard deviation (SD) equal to 4.48 min (ST), 4.73 min (DST) and 5.34 min (seasonal clocks)[4, Figure 1]).

By adopting absolute shifting times, control over the signed shifting time, and thus the original phase, is lost. This is because up and down (signed) regulatory shifts are indistinguishable making the regulation itself irrelevant to this metric. As a result, the metric is mathematically incapable of distinguishing between a stable circadian phase, like the original phase, and a non-regulatory phase that monotonically drifts, see Figure 1 (bottom). These drifting phases would yearly sweep 17.5 h (ST), 20.0 h (DST), and 20.7 h (seasonal clocks). Yet their total absolute shifting times would be the same as in the original phase and would allegedly predict equal epidemiological health issues. This undermines the claim that such an intentional metric possesses a physiological basis.

The statistically grounded way to report the “yearly burden” would have been the SD of the one-year signed differences, noted above. This approach would have exposed the weakness of the magnitudes reported in the original study, only magnified by the yearly accumulation: eventually a yearly burden of 20 h averages to only 3.2 min per day, 0.2% of Earth’s rotation period.

Traditionally the “exposure” to Daylight Saving Time is noted as a (phase) misalignment,[6] a claim we maintain may be flawed.[7, Section 5] Whether intentionally or inadvertently, Weed and Zeitzer[2] test a new approach: treating the variability of the phase as a predictor of epidemiological health issues. Notwithstanding, that the predictor is weak, it is important to highlight that, by design, this approach inevitably yields worst scores for the current clock policy, simply because it is the only policy that tracks the seasonal variability of sunrise and promotes a bimodal phase aligned to seasons, thereby increasing variability of the phase, see Figure 1 (top). Pre-modern naturalistic behaviour more aligned to sunrise would score similarly. Yet again, the paradox arises that adapting to varying ambient light conditions results in greater “burden” scores by design, effectively treating Earth’s axial tilt and latitude as health hazards.

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Figure 1. Top: the original phase CBT_{\min} (hour of the minimum core body temperature) as obtained from the code available in Ref. [2] for San Francisco, intermediate chronotype, and the three clock policies. The signal is stable with a perceptible small fluctuation, aside from transition dates in the rightmost panel. The wavy curve shows sunrise time computed from Ref. [5]. One tick in the vertical scale is $\delta = 5$ min, the time step of the model. Bottom: the same as in the top panels but including two non-regulatory phases with the exact same absolute shifting time as the original phase (OP) but monotonic behavior: the delayed phase (DP) and the advanced phase (AP). DP and AP are obtained from the daily shifting times of OP $\Delta_i = CBT_{\min}[i+1] - CBT_{\min}[i]$, with $i \in [1, 364]$ and the initial phase $CBT_{\min}[1]$. Vertical axis is always set to Standard Time (ST). The total absolute shifting times are 17.5 h per year (2.88 min per day, or 0.20 %, ST); 20.0 h (3.3 min, 0.23 %, DST); 20.7 h (3.40 min, 0.24 %, seasonal clocks).

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

All authors contributed equally to this work.

DECLARATION OF INTEREST

The authors declare no competing interest.

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MANUSCRIPT'S TIME LINE

On Friday April 17 2026 we learned of the reply offered by Weed and Zeitzer [1]. While we appreciated their response, we find it scientifically weak and unspecific. We engaged in the writing of a rejoinder, that we offer here.

The writing of the manuscript required 24 different `emacs` sessions from 2026-04-15 20:39 to 2026-04-22 23:08 .